

RUTTER Stories: Insights from the Team's Personal Experiences

The [RUTTER Project](#)

Early modern nautical rutters (sailing directions) are the earliest Western documents that testify to the stable and regular lived experience of traversing the earth's oceans on a global, planetary scale. Nautical rutters (and ship's logbooks) are technical documents that collect and analyse critical information for the successful accomplishment of oceanic navigation. This includes elements of strict nautical nature (courses, distances, and latitudes), as well as information on oceanography (currents and tides), meteorology (winds and storms), geography, geophysics (magnetic declination) and the natural world. Their unique value lies not only in the fact that they are exceptional historical repositories of information about the world on a planetary scale but, more importantly, that they document the emergence of global concepts about the earth. In fact, no earlier documents contain information about the earth on a comparable worldwide scale. Thus, their historical value is peerless. Using these exceptional, yet poorly known sources, the main objective of this project is to write a narrative of the scaling up of a scientific description of the earth in the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries, from the lived experience of travelling and observing the earth in long-distance sea voyages.

Watch the video about the RUTTER [here](#).

The RUTTER project has received funding from the [European Research Council](#) (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (grant agreement No. 833438).

© ERC RUTTER Project 2025

Authors: Silvana Munzi, Juan Acevedo, Inês Bénard, Luana Giurgevich, Carmo Lacerda, David Salomoni, Nuno Vila-Santa

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.17476784

Silvana Munzi

RUTTER Project Manager

I am a biologist with a PhD in Environmental Science, and I worked as a researcher in the field of lichenology until 2019, when I became the project manager in the RUTTER project. Was the RUTTER project linked or close to my research field? Not at all. Quite simply, the reason that pushed me to apply for the position was the end of my research contract. Instead, the reason I obtained the position competing with professional project managers is that Prof. Henrique Leitão evaluated my CV with an open mind and was able to recognize the potential contribution I could bring to the project. In fact, from the beginning of my career, I have been involved in nearly every aspect of scientific production and communication. My experience spans all stages of a research project: from proposal writing to project management and reporting, from outreach and public engagement to organizing scientific events. I am familiar with the operational frameworks of various European funding programs and serve actively in multiple scientific societies and associations. All these skills have been tested and significantly strengthened through my work within the RUTTER project.

In brief, I considered that my job was making the lives of the RUTTER team members as simple as possible. That's what project managers do: they remove external obstacles so that researchers are in the best position to carry out their work. However, I'm a scientist, and my nature emerged between one management task and the other. Thus, these past years have become a journey during which not only I've learned a great deal about the fascinating subject of the RUTTER project, but I

also gained a taste for history of science and learnt that there is so much in this field linked to my research interests.

With the support of Prof. Leitão, I completed small research tasks within the project, contributed to its outputs and organized outreach activities. The differences between my original research area and the field of History of Science allowed me to explore new approaches and tools, such as archival research, digital humanities and new forms of communication. Stepping out of my comfort zone made of microscopes, hand-lens and iNaturalist required me to turn to unfamiliar dissemination tools. In this sense, the collaboration with the Faculty of Science's Theater Company for a staged reading, and the paleography contest during the Pint of Science event are two activities of which I'm particularly satisfied.

The daily collaboration with the project members has been also a wonderful exercise of mentoring. I shared my experience with them, offered guidance on different aspects of their work, identified opportunities and supported them in preparing proposals. They also reinforced my problem-solving skills, constantly challenging me to find practical solutions, adapt quickly, and support the team in dynamic and sometimes unexpected situations. I feel that we have grown together, both personally and professionally.

An ERC project is the perfect environment to learn and develop your skills, whatever your role is in the project. You have all the resources, the support and the freedom to do so. Working on the RUTTER project showed me that I can have a meaningful role in science, even if not as a researcher, broadening my professional horizons for the future.

Thank you, Henrique Leitão. Thank you, RUTTER. Thank you, European Research Council.

Watch the video about Silvana [here](#).

Luana Giurgevich

RUTTER Researcher

Being a member of the RUTTER Project has had a profound impact on my professional life. It allowed me to deepen my expertise in the study of early modern maritime technical literature, helping me establish myself as an internationally recognized specialist in this field. This experience broadened my academic profile and enabled innovative research across a wide range of archives scattered throughout Europe — from London to Rome and Simancas — many of which remain largely inaccessible to most scholars. These institutions preserve extensive and underexplored collections, much of which has neither been digitized nor catalogued online. In many cases, the only way to access the materials is by consulting handwritten indexes and inventories that are centuries old and available exclusively on site. Without the material and financial support of the ERC RUTTER Project, it would have been practically impossible for a researcher based in Portugal to work in such demanding and resource-intensive research environments and to access rare manuscripts and texts that would otherwise be difficult to study.

Moreover, the project connected me to an international network of scholars, greatly enriching both my research and professional development. Before joining the ERC RUTTER Project, my work was much more isolated, with only occasional collaborations with a few colleagues. Being part of the RUTTER team meant engaging daily with a large and diverse group of researchers. My colleagues came from diverse national and academic backgrounds, bringing with them different perspectives,

methodologies, and areas of expertise. This diversity fostered a truly multilingual and intellectually stimulating environment. Such a setting not only enhanced the quality of our collective research but also broadened my own capacity to work across linguistic and cultural boundaries, a skill that has proved invaluable for engaging with early modern sources and international academic discourse alike.

Concrete outcomes of my involvement include invitations to publish papers and present my research internationally, such as the one at the School of Advanced Study of the University of London in May 2023 (European History 1500-1800 seminar series). Conducting research within the framework of the ERC RUTTER Project also fostered closer collaborations with prestigious institutions and led to the publication of my work by the Portuguese Academia da Marinha (currently in press). Furthermore, the project opened up new professional opportunities, including a collaboration with the Fundação Gaudium Magnum (Lisbon), with which I am currently under contract.

I coordinated and contributed to the training of new generations of scholars in archival research by organizing regular expeditions to archives and co-organizing trainings such as the training school *The Long Life of Manuscripts*. These initiatives engaged students and scholars from various parts of Europe, fostering an international learning environment. I also took part in structuring inventories, databases, and developing digital tools—such as the *A Sea of Books* website—which significantly enhanced my own academic visibility.

Participating in the daily life of an ERC project means becoming fully immersed in a dynamic and stimulating research environment. It involves engaging with the project's evolving goals, contributing actively to its milestones, and adapting to the rhythm of collaborative academic work. This continuous involvement fosters a strong sense of shared purpose and provides invaluable insight into how high-level international research is structured and carried out.

This experience has also had a lasting effect on how I envision my future as a researcher. Through the ERC RUTTER Project, I not only deepened my expertise but also gained the confidence and skills to lead my own research initiatives. It sharpened my understanding of what innovative, collaborative, and impactful scholarship can look like. I now feel better equipped to pursue competitive international funding, to build cross-border research networks, and mentor new generations of scholars. Most importantly, it has reinforced my commitment to making underexplored historical sources more accessible, and to continuing to bridge the gap between archival research and digital tools, between scholars and society.

Watch the video about Luana [here](#).

Nuno Vila-Santa

RUTTER Researcher

My involvement as a post-doctoral researcher in the ERC Advanced Grant *RUTTER – Making the Earth Global* had a profound impact on both my research methodology and professional development. Before joining the RUTTER project, I had participated in interdisciplinary initiatives, albeit for brief periods, where I had the opportunity to collaborate with colleagues from diverse fields such as Literature, Art History, Anthropology, and Sociology. Trained as a historian, joining RUTTER presented an immediate challenge, as it was a History of Science project, and I had never previously worked alongside historians of science. In this sense, applying for the position was a personal challenge, as I would be working in a field unfamiliar to me. Upon joining the team, I was initially surprised to discover that most of my colleagues were in a similar situation. Most team members (excluding the Principal Investigator) were not historians of science. Instead, the team consisted of scholars from early modern literature, Ancient linguistics, historians of education, and historians such as myself.

Additionally, the team was truly international, comprising researchers from Portugal, Spain, Italy, and Venezuela. This was one of the most significant outcomes of working in an ERC-funded project: we found ourselves collaborating with individuals from a wide range of academic backgrounds, which always proves to be an enriching experience both academically and personally. The project's interdisciplinary nature, combined with the PI's exceptional ability to integrate and connect our varied

academic expertise with the project's overarching goals, fostered an environment of continuous dialogue, mutual support, and collaboration.

Whenever any team member had a question—whether basic or complex—we simply reached out to each other and received prompt responses. Conversations, whether during lunch breaks or in our weekly meetings, were always intellectually stimulating, as we continuously learned new insights from our colleagues. This collaborative atmosphere, which I have only encountered to such an extent in projects funded by ERC grants, created a productive environment for academic exchange. As a result, it is not surprising that many of us, including myself, ended up co-authoring publications. This collaborative dimension, which promotes the complementarity of knowledge and facilitates exchange among international researchers, was a central feature of the project's success.

However, working in this environment also challenged my previous working methods, which had been shaped by my earlier academic training. I was part of a team where colleagues were consistently available to offer support and encouragement, both in moments of success and during the inevitable challenges that arise in research. In essence, I was not working in isolation, as I had so often done in the past. This shift initially represented a challenge, but ended up easing my work. Ultimately it clarified why I was invited to take on a co-leadership role within the project. The Principal Investigator's vision, which involved assigning different lines of research to each post-doctoral researcher, quickly led to my responsibility for guiding junior students, including MA and PhD candidates, as well as interns. This was a new challenge for me, one that had not been part of my previous academic experience but that fully rewarding: the opportunity to motivate and mentor younger students in their research endeavors.

Another key benefit of ERC funding for me and my colleagues was the opportunity to travel for archival research and attend international conferences. For the first time in my career, I had the resources to visit archives in Spain, France, the UK, and Italy—archives that had previously been inaccessible due to financial constraints. Additionally, I was able to attend international conferences in the USA, the UK, and Ireland, opportunities that had been beyond my reach for similar reasons. RUTTER, therefore, provided me with two invaluable advantages: access to foreign archives, enabling me to conduct research that was previously unattainable, and the opportunity to participate in international conferences, where I could engage with prominent scholars in my field. The professional contacts I made through these experiences continue to be significant for my academic work. These interactions led to the establishment of new partnerships, the exchange of ideas, and the development of forthcoming scholarly outputs.

The project financial resources also allowed me to improve my academic English writing and speaking skills while producing outputs in this language. The articles I published in journals indexed in *Web of Science* and *Scopus*, as well as my final monograph at AUP, were direct outcomes of the collaborative environment fostered by RUTTER, as well as the opportunities offered by ERC funding. However, the benefits of these outputs were not limited to the project alone—they also had a significant impact on my academic career. Through RUTTER, I published my first English-language monograph, gained my first experience in mentoring young researchers, won a prize in Portugal, and established international collaborations that had previously been out of reach. While all these achievements were made possible by RUTTER, they also contributed to enhancing my CV in ways I had not experienced before. Ultimately, the project played a crucial role in advancing my career, culminating in my securing a second post-doctoral position within another ERC-funded project. In conclusion, I can confidently say that my participation in RUTTER enabled me to grow both as a scholar and as an individual.

It is important to remember the pivotal moment when the RUTTER Principal Investigator secured the ERC grant. At that time, I believe he could not have fully anticipated the profound impact that the project would have on the careers of the researchers he was about to hire. Ultimately, the greatest reward offered by ERC funding is the opportunity to build a team and engage in collaborative work on a scale, dimension and impact that national funding programs can scarcely match.

Watch the video about Nuno [here](#).

Juan Acevedo

RUTTER Researcher

What has been the impact on my career of working for an ERC project? My answer has to come with a caveat, because I am very aware of how ERC projects can differ significantly. No two teams are equal, host institutions are unlike any other, PIs are decisive, and so, within a general common administrative framework, many variables can go different ways.

So, caveat: In our particular case, as a team, we were extremely fortunate to count on the leadership and guidance of a most experienced PI who is not only a researcher but also a great educator. This for us has made all the difference, because from day one we were inculcated with an inspiring and challenging “ERC ethos” or “ERC mentality”, at once making us proud and humble. Proud to belong to a small group of very specialised cutting-edge researchers; humble before the formidable scholars in whose league we suddenly found ourselves. At first, I assumed that this was how every ERC worked, but over the years I realised that it was highly uncommon, and that it was a deliberate educational strategy from our PI.

More personally, having come from philosophy and philology, embarking on an ERC in history of nautical science and technology meant for me to apply my skills to a totally new area of research. And so for me, joining the team meant the exhilaration of acquiring in the briefest time a great amount of new information, new sources, new repositories. After this initial induction, I started to gradually weave my new knowledge into areas of my previous work, and this has been and continues

to be a fascinating task. In fact, my work for the Project has turned to be also an academic springboard, and last year I obtained a six-year individual grant (FCT CEEC programme) to continue developing the research line that was under my lead.

Being by nature a team worker, I took to heart from the beginning the “common good” of the project, and so for me working at the project meant also collaborating in various tasks where my skills could be useful. This meant that working at the ERC project never had for me a feeling of “ivory tower”, but rather of intense engagement with scholars who were my seniors, my peers and my juniors, both intellectually, as in multidisciplinary collaboration, and administratively. This multiple engagement was very fulfilling, because I was in fact bringing into action, in this new work environment, various competencies honed over the years inside and outside academia.

Trying to summarize and give a general view, I would say that the project expanded enormously my research scope and my network, and it set me off on an academic course which I am continuing to pursue. This while also encouraging me, and giving me the means to fulfill my potential on several fronts, both academic and para-academic. Once again, I attribute a great part of this positive impact to the work of our PI.

Looking back on these five years fills me with gratitude, professionally and humanly—what a great intellectual and collegial adventure we have shared!

Watch the video about Juan [here](#).

David Salomoni

RUTTER Researcher

Working on the ERC project *RUTTER: Making the Earth Global*, based at the Department of History and Philosophy of Science of the University of Lisbon, has had a significant impact on my career in several ways. I would say, in this regard, that it has been the most important professional experience in my career to date. I was awarded the postdoctoral fellowship within the aforementioned ERC project in the autumn of 2019, and began working full-time in January 2020 until March 2023. Since then, I have continued to be part of the research team as an external, non-funded member.

I arrived in Lisbon as a historian of early modern education, with a research focus primarily centred on a local context (northern Italy). Working within an ERC-funded project enabled me to expand and enhance my existing expertise by placing it in a fully global research framework. Thanks to the leadership of the Principal Investigator, Henrique Leitão, and to collaboration with colleagues from all over the world, I was able to develop my skills in new and unexpected directions, generating original solutions in line with the spirit of innovation that characterizes ERC research.

Within a history of science project aimed at investigating the emergence of the concept of globality in the early modern period, I managed to carve out a niche of research focused on the theme of geographical literacy in the same period, an equally innovative and original line of inquiry. I would not have been able to develop this research independently, outside the ERC framework. The financial, intellectual, and human resources that I was able to access through the ERC profoundly redefined my

approach to historical research, placing at the heart of my practice the need to find new research perspectives, or to critically reshape existing ones.

This experience also pushed me to look at the methods and purposes of my humanistic work through the lens of a scientist, seeking connections between research and the real world in which we live. These transformations were not only theoretical, but also had concrete effects on my career. Thanks to the skills I acquired during my time in the project, and to the overall professional growth I experienced, in 2023 I won a Tenure Track position in Italy, becoming an Assistant Professor with a stable and long-term academic perspective. This achievement, too, would not have been possible without my experience in the ERC project.

After obtaining the position, I continued to collaborate with the project as an external associate. My work did not stop there: I have continued to carry forward research initiatives launched within the ERC framework, such as a collective volume that will soon be published in Open Access, made possible thanks to ERC funding. This has allowed me to gain greater visibility in the wider European and American academic communities and to expand my professional network beyond what I had previously imagined.

Moreover, during the project, I began writing history books aimed at a broader, non-academic audience on the topic of exploration voyages. These books were later published in Italy, my country of origin, allowing me to disseminate the themes of my research to a wide readership and opening up career opportunities as a public historian that I could not have imagined just a few years ago.

Finally, the methodological and collaborative skills I developed—both in terms of research and of working within a research team—enabled me to submit my own ERC project proposal earlier this year. For this reason too, my time in Lisbon proved to be fundamental.

Watch the video about David [here](#).

Inês Bénard

RUTTER PhD Student

This note is being written at the end of a long journey. I first entered the ERC RUTTER project as a volunteer member working part-time and searching for PhD programs abroad. Portugal was not an option by then, for there were not opportunities to one wanting to study topics related to history of Arabic science and circulation of knowledge. I knew that. But then it happened that the former supervisor of my master's degree was just starting his new project on oceanic rutters, which so happened to have a clear interest in studying Arab treatises; and it also happened that he had just hired Juan Acevedo for the job. Six years later, that which began as a work on the side developed into my PhD dissertation supervised by Henrique Leitão and Juan together. The chance to work with the two and with the incredible group of scholars who integrated RUTTER had a major impact in the historian I am now becoming. It helped me to improve my academic skills, strive to acquire new ones, explore research interests, and to draw my own path. This note is a letter of gratitude to the RUTTER team and to the European Research Council.

The importance that the past six years have had in my early career as a scholar is perhaps made clearer through an image of the academic environment as I was working in. The most basic feature of it all were the people assembled around the project. RUTTER had an interdisciplinary team where each member carried different interests and skills with one broad topic in common. This element alone fostered discussions where questions, ideas, and suggestions often came up. The project

counted likewise with an impressive group of advisors and associate members such as José Malhão Pereira, Dionisius Agius, and Eric Staples, with whom I was fortunate to discuss topics of my own research.

The environment set by RUTTER was constituted by a second key aspect, which was the constant promotion of activities designed to improve academic skills and work. This included encouragement and support to attend conferences and workshops, helping me to learn how to better discuss work with colleagues, receive feedback, and strive to improve. Aside from this, there were periodic sessions of paleography, Latin and Arabic for those interested in these skills. The longest of the three, and the most important for my work, was a reading group of maritime and astronomical texts in Arabic: a group of international scholars continues to gather today over zoom to discuss, read, and translate historical sources together. This was undoubtedly the most efficient means for me to become acquainted with the nautical vocabulary I required to develop my research.

The last aspect I would underline in this note is the learning and working opportunities the project generated, which would hardly have been possible otherwise. Here I just mention the three I consider to have been most outstanding. The first appeared at the beginning of my participation in RUTTER, before I enrolled in the PhD program. The project granted me with an Arabic summer course in Jordan to pursue my language studies. The second happened more towards the middle of my research, when the curator of the Gulbenkian Museum in Lisbon, Jessica Hallet invited me and Juan to work on an exhibition with her. She was looking for Arabists who could look at an unusual manuscript and heard about us through our participation in RUTTER. The third opportunity came about later, when I was accepted to spend a short-time period in Zayed University in Abu Dhabi in order to work with Professor Eric Staples in a yet unpublished edition of an Arab nautical treatise, and where I also received valuable input for my doctoral research. These were three key periods of intense work which have stimulated my academic performance in ways I had not anticipated at the beginning.

The list of aspects defining RUTTER as an enriching experience goes on. I could talk about the missions to archives, the internal seminars, the invited scholars, the facilities, the books, and more. I stop here instead not to make this note too long and just acknowledge that all that I have mentioned in the previous lines – from the assembly of the team to the academic conferences – every detail was made possible ultimately because there was one PI who had the vision and the financial ability to allow for it to happen.

Six years have passed. I moved from being a master student working part-time, to winning a scholarship by the Portuguese Foundation of Science and Technology (FCT) to, now, closing a PhD research on a topic I am truly fascinated about. I owe this to RUTTER, to Henrique Leitão, and to the European Research Council.

Watch the video about Inês [here](#).

Carmo Lacerda

RUTTER PhD Student

When first I arrived at the RUTTER Project, I didn't know what academic life or scholarly work entailed, nor did I know what the ERC was. I only knew I had an interest in the History of Science and a desire to learn more, which is why I had enrolled in the Master's program. When I approached Professor Henrique Leitão to supervise my dissertation, he told me he had just received funding for a project (an ERC Advanced Grant) and that he had a team working on nautical rutters from the Early Modern Period in the Iberian Peninsula. He asked if I wanted to join the team meetings to get a sense of what academic work was like. I agreed, of course, and suddenly I found myself a member of the ERC Project *RUTTER: Making the Earth Global*. I completed my Master's within the scope of this project, collaborating on a voluntary basis, and later remained involved as a PhD student.

The ERC made it possible for me to grow inside an academic oasis in my city, at my university, in my department—one that allowed me to understand how excellent academic research works and gave me the ideal conditions to take my first steps in this field, surrounded by outstanding role models.

I had the privilege of joining an international team of exceptional researchers, with diverse academic backgrounds, and at different stages of their careers. Throughout the project, every researcher had the chance to share their knowledge and research during the "RUTTER Seminars." These seminars were incredibly enriching for me, not just because of the content presented, but also because I could witness how experienced scholars worked and received feedback.

Another major privilege made possible by this ERC project was the close interaction with leading academics abroad who specialize in RUTTER-related fields or adjacent historical topics. I benefited from these encounters both in person—when the project invited these scholars to give seminars at our university—and online, through informal sessions we called “Scholar Meets RUTTER.” Thanks to the project, I had the opportunity to meet and engage with top researchers and expand my academic horizons.

One of the most valuable experiences RUTTER provided was working with historical archives. With the support of my colleagues and through hands-on experience, I began to understand how archives function and how to make the most of them for research purposes. Alongside some of my peers, I helped catalogue relevant sources at the Ajuda Library, which greatly enhanced my archival research skills and deepened my appreciation for this aspect of historical research.

Another important skill I developed with the help of my teammates was paleography. RUTTER gave me my first contact with 16th-century texts, and I was encouraged from the beginning to familiarize myself with this type of writing by transcribing documents. We also created a paleography group, where we read and analyzed documents from that era. One of my colleagues generously led this group, sharing his extensive knowledge with us, and thanks to this I can now fluently read documents from the 16th and 17th centuries.

Similarly, a Latin reading group emerged within the RUTTER team, led by another project member, who taught us the fundamentals necessary to read Latin texts.

RUTTER also strongly embraced Digital Humanities, constantly encouraging us to explore digital tools that could aid our work and help disseminate the knowledge we were building through our studies. We thus began a series of digital editions of key texts for the project, which we transcribed using tools like Transkribus and made accessible and searchable for the broader academic community. Beyond the great benefit of having these texts in digital format, it was also a valuable learning opportunity for me to engage with new tools.

One of the most remarkable benefits Rutter gave me—and one I’d dare say is a dream for any PhD student—was the seemingly infinite library. Having the means to acquire the books and articles I needed for my research, and watching a library filled with essential and cutting-edge works grow around me week after week, was truly extraordinary, useful and convenient.

RUTTER gave me the opportunity to attend major conferences, such as the Renaissance Society of America annual meeting, and this allowed me to learn how the top researchers in the world deliver their presentations. Thanks to Rutter, I was also able to present my own work at conferences

abroad, with registration, travel, and accommodation costs covered by the project. I feel incredibly fortunate to have had these conditions—something rare in Portugal unless you are part of an ERC project. Without that support, I almost certainly wouldn't have gone.

At RUTTER, we constantly received constructive and meaningful feedback—from our Principal Investigator, the Project Manager, and our peers—on our work, presentations, and publications. We also got valuable advice on how to successfully pursue our goals, applications, and career development from the very beginning. This support enabled me to win a doctoral scholarship, funded by FCT, which guarantees me the continuity of my research even when RUTTER ends.

I can say that most of my still-early academic path has taken place within an ERC project—RUTTER—and I say this with great pride, as well as a deep awareness of the privilege I've had in being part of it. This is not only due to the exceptional resources an ERC grant provides, but also to the outstanding academic environment fostered within RUTTER, starting with Professor Henrique Leitão's wise leadership and extending to every project member. This atmosphere wasn't only defined by academic excellence but also by the genuinely human and generous nature of the team. In a true spirit of shared knowledge, everyone contributed freely with what they knew and had, always in a climate of trust and mutual support, without the rivalry so often present in academic circles. I am truly lucky to have had this team during these foundational years of my academic life—people I could turn to with questions, whether about research specifics or broader existential doubts about life in academia.

Growing within RUTTER was a genuine privilege. It allowed me to witness top-level academic research firsthand. For everything I experienced and learned through this project and this wonderful team, I owe immense gratitude to Professor Henrique Leitão, the entire team, and the ERC.

Watch the video about Carmo [here](#).